

Raney Nickel Desulphuration of 1-Substituted- and 1,3-Disubstituted-thioureas

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Certain 1-aryl-1,3-diaryl- and 1-aryl-3-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl thioureas have been successfully desulphurated into the related mono- and 1,3-di-substituted formamidines with the help of Raney nickel catalyst. A few of them have been converted into the corresponding formamides also. Structure of the products have been established through usual chemical transformations, ir, nmr and mass spectral analysis.

RECENTLY, we have reported desulphuration of some 1-arylthiourea (1) in the presence of Raney nickel (W-2) in boiling ethanol leading to the corresponding 1-arylformamides (4)¹. These arylformamides have been suggested to be formed through arylformamidine intermediates. The present paper describes the desulphuration of the above 1-arylthioureas as well as certain 1,3-diaryl- and 1-aryl-3-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl thioureas with the help of Raney nickel catalyst in boiling benzene medium. In all cases the related formamidines have been isolated.

1-Aryl- and 1-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-formamidines (2): 1-*p*-Chlorophenylthiourea (1a) on desulphuration with Raney nickel (W-2) in boiling benzene gave *p*-chlorophenylformamidine (2a). On boiling with ethanol it gave *p*-chloroaniline. When boiled with Raney nickel in ethanol, it gave *p*-chlorophenyl formamide (4a) and *p*-chloroaniline. Ir spectrum showed characteristic bands at 3400 (NH) and 1630 cm⁻¹ (C=N)²⁻⁴. Nmr spectrum showed signals at δ 8.07 (1H, RNH-CH=NH) and 6.90-7.32 (Ar-H).

When 1-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosylthiourea (1g) was desulphurated with Raney nickel (W-2) in boiling benzene medium, it gave a semi-solid mass which solidified on keeping in vacuum desiccator for 30 days. It was assigned 1-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosylformamidine structure, [α]_D²⁰ = +20.78; ν_{\max} 3360 (NH), 1735 (C=O), 1660, 1268, 890 cm⁻¹ (β -anomer of glucopyranosyl ring)²⁻⁶; δ 8.22 (1H, NH-CH=NH), 7.36-7.29 (1H, NH) and 2.03 (12H, 4-O-CO-CH₃ equatorial)^{2,7,8}.

On extending this Raney nickel desulphuration reaction to several other 1-arylthioureas (1b-f), the corresponding 1-arylformamidines (2b-f) have been isolated (Table 1). All these have been successfully converted to the corresponding 1-arylformamide and arylamines.

1,3-Diarylformamidines (6): 1,3-Di-*p*-tolylthiourea (5a) on desulphuration in presence of Raney nickel (W-2) in boiling benzene gave 1,3-di-*p*-tolylformamidine (6a), ν_{\max} 3380 and 1645 cm⁻¹ (Refs. 2-4); δ

where, R = a *p*-chlorophenyl, b *p*-tolyl, c *p*-anisyl, d *m*-chlorophenyl, e *m*-tolyl, f phenyl, g tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl.

2.34 (3H, CH₃ of Ar-ring), 6.84-7.14 (Ar-H) and 8.15 (1H, NH-CH=NH)²; *m/e* 224. Similarly, other symmetrical 1,3-diarylthioureas (5a-f) were desulphurated with Raney nickel (W-2) in boiling benzene medium to the corresponding formamidines (6b-f) (Table 2).

Desulphuration of 1,3-diarylthioureas was investigated in boiling ethanolic medium. 5a and 5b gave formamidines (6a and 6b), while 5c gave formamide 4a. In all other cases the corresponding arylamines have been isolated as decomposition product.

where, R = a *p*-tolyl, b *p*-anisyl, c *p*-chlorophenyl, d *m*-chlorophenyl, e *m*-tolyl, f phenyl.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS AND DERIVATIVES (1, 2, 3 AND 4)*

Thiourea Compd. (g) no.	1-Arylformamidine			N-Bromo derivative			Hydrochloride			Picrate			1-Arylformamide		
	Compd. (g) no.	M.p. °C	Analysis N%: Found/ (Calcd.)	Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Analysis N%: Found/ (Calcd.)	M.p. °C	Eq. wt.: Found/ (Calcd.)	M.p. °C	Analysis N%: Found/ (Calcd.)	Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Analysis N%: Found/ (Calcd.)	Compd. no.	M.p. °C
1a (9.94)	2a (4.0)	188	17.65 (18.12)	3a	106	11.45 (11.99)	316 d	195.2 (191.0)	229 d	18.07 (18.25)	4a	109	18.07 (18.25)	9.25 (9.0)	
b (8.33)	b (8.8)	145*	20.57 (20.89)	b	78	13.92 (18.14)	261 d	172.0 (170.5)	217 d	18.64 (19.28)	b	58	18.64 (19.28)	9.73 (10.37)	
c (9.00)	c (8.7)	122	18.19 (18.66)	c	115	12.02 (12.25)	267	190.0 (185.5)	200 d	18.0 (18.46)	c	85	18.0 (18.46)	9.7 (9.3)	
d (9.94)	d (8.8)	115	17.85 (18.13)	d	125	11.63 (11.99)	279 d	188.0 (191.0)	215 d	18.0 (18.25)	d	65	18.0 (18.25)	9.2 (9.0)	
e (8.33)	e (8.9)	132	20.85 (20.89)	e	105	12.76 (13.14)	235 d	165.2 (170.5)	205	19.55 (19.28)	e	178	19.55 (19.28)	10.5 (10.37)	
f (7.66)	f (8.6)	143	22.74 (23.83)	f	122	13.74 (14.07)	238	160.0 (156.5)	190	19.67 (20.05)	f	47	19.67 (20.05)	11.0 (11.57)	
g (8.1)	g (5.1)	126	7.21 (7.49)	—	—	—	Not isolated	—	272 d	11.32 (11.61)	—	—	—	—	

* Satisfactory C and H values obtained. * Lit. 138-35°.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS AND DERIVATIVES (6)*

1,3-Diaryl thionrea Compd. (g) no.	1,3-Diarylformamidine			Hydrochloride			Amidine derivative		
	Compd. (g) no.	M.p. °C	Analysis N%: Found/ (Calcd.)	M.p. °C	Eq. wt.: Found/ (Calcd.)	M.p. °C	Compd. (g) no.	M.p. °C	Analysis N%: Found/ (Calcd.)
5a 12.8 (0.05)	6a (8.9)	147	11.92 (12.50)	269 d	264.2 (260.5)	220 d	15.10 (15.45)		
b 14.4 (0.05)	b (8.7)	112	10.89 (10.98)	270 d	285.0 (292.5)	202 d	14.89 (14.43)		
c 14.8 (0.05)	c (8.9)	185	10.17 (10.49)	290 d	310.7 (301.5)	243 d	18.89 (14.08)		
d 14.8 (0.05)	d (8.8)	121	10.63 (10.49)	285	290.0 (301.5)	227 d	14.25 (14.08)		
e 12.8 (0.05)	e (8.3)	190	11.95 (12.50)	238	252.0 (260.5)	202	15.48 (15.42)		
f 11.4 (0.05)	f (5.9)	141	13.66 (14.28)	248 d	229.3 (232.5)	193 d	15.98 (16.37)		

* Satisfactory C and H values obtained.

TABLE 3—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS AND DERIVATIVES (8 AND 9)*

1-TAG-3-substituted-thiourea		1-TAG-3-substituted-formamidine		N-Bromo derivative			Picrate	
Compd. (g) no.	Compd. (g) no.	M.p. °C	Analysis N% : Found/Calcd.	Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Analysis N% : Found/Calcd.	M.p. °C	Analysis N% : Found/Calcd.
7a (10.8)	8a (6.9)	74	5.84 (5.78)	9a	110	5.28 (4.97)	186-8	9.57 (9.81)
b (9.6)	b (6.3)	82	5.93 (6.22)	b	123	5.12 (5.28)	184 d	10.73 (10.30)
c (9.9)	c (6.4)	81	5.79 (6.04)	c	84	4.89 (5.15)	168 d	10.27 (10.10)
d (9.9)	d (6.2)	94	5.85 (6.04)	d	56	5.65 (5.15)	167	9.67 (10.10)
e (10.3)	e (6.6)	106	5.51 (5.78)	e	110	4.75 (4.96)	189	10.02 (9.81)
f (10.03)	f (6.5)	97	5.26 (5.78)	f	125	4.59 (4.96)	170 d	9.94 (9.81)
g (9.5)	g (6.0)	116	6.03 (6.30)	Not isolated			250 d	10.65 (10.38)
h (9.5)	h (6.1)	103	6.18 (6.35)	Not isolated			260	10.18 (10.41)

* Satisfactory O and H values obtained.

1-Tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-3-arylformamidines (8): 1-Tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-3-*p*-chlorophenylthiourea (7a) when desulphurated in presence of Raney nickel (W-2) in boiling benzene medium, gave 1-tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-3-*p*-chlorophenyl formamidine, $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +55.78$; λ_{max} 250 nm; ν_{max} 3400, 1740 (C=O), 1650, 1350 and 900 cm^{-1} (Ref. 2-6); δ 8.22 (1H, NH-CH=NH), 7.36 (1H, NH), 2.03 (3H, O-CO-CH₃, equatorial) and 4.9-5.35 (β -glucopyranosyl)^{2,7,8}.

When Raney nickel desulphuration reaction was extended to other 1-tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-3-substituted-thioureas (7b-h), the corresponding formamidines (8b-h) were isolated (Table 3).

where, R = a *p*-chlorophenyl, b phenyl, c *p*-tolyl, d *o*-tolyl, e *o*-chlorophenyl, f *m*-chlorophenyl, g 4-morpholinyl, h piperidyl, Ac = Acetyl.

Experimental

The required 1-arylthioureas were prepared by the interaction of ammonium thiocyanate and arylamine hydrochloride⁹. The required 1-tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl thiourea¹⁰ was prepared according to the procedure developed in this laboratory. The symmetrical 1,3-diarylthioureas were prepared by the interaction of arylamine and carbon disulphide¹¹. Phenyl isothiocyanate was

prepared by the oxidative decomposition of ammonium phenyl dithiocarbamate¹². The 1-tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-3-arylthioureas were prepared by the interaction of tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate and the corresponding arylamines in boiling benzene medium¹⁰. Raney nickel (W-2) was prepared following the procedure described by Mozingo¹³.

1-Arylformamidines (2): A hot solution of 1a (0.05 mol, 9.34 g) in benzene (50 ml) was added to a suspension of Raney nickel (W-2; 24 g) in benzene (150 ml) and the mixture refluxed with constant stirring for 150 min when a red coloured solution of the desulphurated product was obtained. The solvent was then distilled off and the reddish residue was washed carefully with ethanol and finally crystallised from a mixture of benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 1).

N-Bromo derivative (3): In a typical experiment (where, aryl = *p*-chlorophenyl) 2a (0.5 g) in ethanol (10.0 ml) was heated with 10% bromine solution in acetic acid, and the reaction mixture was kept overnight. A needle shaped product (0.7 g) of *N*-bromo-*p*-chlorophenylformamidine was isolated and crystallised from ethanol.

1-Arylformamide (4): Solution of 2a (3.0 g) in ethanol (20 ml) was added to a suspension of Raney nickel (W-2; 8.0 g) in ethanol (30.0 ml) and the mixture was refluxed over boiling water for 60 min. The solvent was then distilled off and a viscous residue was obtained, which on standing overnight was converted into a granular solid (4a; 1.9 g). It was washed with cold dilute HCl (4 N) and then crystallised from glacial acetic acid. The acidic filtrate on basification with cold dilute ammonium hydroxide solution gave *p*-chloroaniline, m.p. 70° (Found: N, 11.03. C₆H₆NCl calcd. N, 10.98%).

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